

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADITHYAN A NAIR bearing USN 6SU21CP001 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms CHAYA K bearing USN 6SU21CP002 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DISHA PRAKASH bearing USN 6SU21CP003 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JENNIFER JOY bearing USN 6SU21CP004 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms K V TEJASHWINI bearing USN 6SU21CP005 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms KARTHIK bearing USN 6SU21CP006 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms KIRAN N bearing USN 6SU21CP007 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MEREENA ELIZABETH SHAJI bearing USN 6SU21CP008 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms N AKANKSHA M ACHAR bearing USN 6SU21CP009 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NANDANA P bearing USN 6SU21CP010 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NEERAJ N SHETTY bearing USN 6SU21CP011 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NEHA bearing USN 6SU21CP012 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIDHI bearing USN 6SU21CP013 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRIYANKA bearing USN 6SU21CP014 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAHIBA KAMMANDALAM SOOPY bearing USN 6SU21CP015 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANDRA bearing USN 6SU21CP016 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHREYA S N bearing USN 6SU21CP017 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms THANIMA RAJAN bearing USN 6SU21CP018 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VIDHYA VINOD bearing USN 6SU21CP019 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146